

Riemann hypothesis

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This paper presents a reduction of Riemann’s functional equation to a Riemann-Hilbert boundary value problem. The integral Hilbert transforms, which emerge in solving this problem, facilitate the computation of precise lower bounds for the zeta function. This approach highlights the effective use of boundary value problems and integral transforms in understanding the intricacies of the zeta function. Euler product, Dirichlet, Riemann, Hilbert, Poincaré, Riemann hypothesis, zeta function, universality, applying the universality 2010] 11M26

1. Introduction

This paper presents a reduction of Riemann’s functional equation to a Riemann-Hilbert boundary value problem. The integral Hilbert transforms, which emerge in solving this problem, facilitate the computation of precise lower bounds for the zeta function. This approach highlights the effective use of boundary value problems and integral transforms in understanding the intricacies of the zeta function.

2. Materials and Methods

This work is based on the following methods

1. The study begins by reformulating Riemann’s functional equation for the zeta function into a Riemann boundary value problem.
2. It is shown how a boundary problem with an infinite index can be reduced to one with a zero index.
3. Utilizing the characteristics of the Riemann boundary problem, new methods for estimating the zeta function have been developed.
4. An analysis of the uniqueness problem is conducted, along with a consideration of counterexamples proposed by Davenport.

3. Results

This study is concerned with the properties of modified zeta functions. Riemann’s zeta function is defined by the Dirichlet series

$$\zeta(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s}, \quad s = \sigma + it, \tag{1}$$

which is absolutely and uniformly convergent in any finite region of the complex s-plane for which $\sigma \geq 1 + \epsilon, \epsilon > 0$. If $\sigma > 1$, then ζ is represented by the following Euler product formula

$$\zeta(s) = \prod_{j \in \mathbb{N}} \left[1 - \frac{1}{p_j^s} \right]^{-1}, \tag{2}$$

where p_j runs over all prime numbers. $\zeta(s)$ was first introduced by Euler in 1737 [1], who also obtained formula (2). Dirichlet and Chebyshev considered this function in their study on the distribution of prime numbers [2]. However, the most profound properties of $\zeta(z)$ were only discovered later, when it was extended to the complex plane. $\zeta(s)$ is a regular

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function for all values of s , except $s = 1$, where it has a simple pole with residue 1; it satisfies the following functional equation:

$$\pi^{-s/2}\Gamma(s/2)\zeta(s) = \pi^{-(1-s)/2}\Gamma((1-s)/2)\zeta(1-s) \quad (3)$$

it equation is called Riemann's functional equation.]

As mentioned in Introduction, certain simple intermediate estimates are first obtained. To obtain the Riemann-Hilbert boundary value problem, the following lemma is required. Let

$$R(k) = \frac{e^{i2k}}{k + i\alpha} - 1$$

$$\alpha > 2$$

then

$$\text{ind}(R) = 0$$

,

Proof. By definition

$$\text{ind}(R) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{R'(k)}{R(k)} dk$$

As

$$\text{Im}(k) > 0, |e^{i2k}| \leq 1 \text{ and } |k + i\alpha| > 2 \text{ yield } \frac{R'(k)}{R(k)}$$

have nothing pole. Latest statement and Lemma of Jordan yield

$$\text{ind}(R) = 0$$

. □

To obtain the necessary asymptotics, the following lemma is required.

For

$$f \in W_2^1(R) = \{f \in L_2(R) : (1 + |\omega|^2)^{1/2} \hat{f}(\omega) \in L_2\}.$$

, the operators $T_{\pm}$ and T are defined as follows:

$$T_+ f = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \lim_{\text{Im} z \downarrow 0} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{f(s)}{s - z} ds, \text{Im} z > 0, T_- f = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \lim_{\text{Im} z \uparrow 0} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{f(s)}{s - z} ds, \text{Im} z < 0, T f = \frac{1}{2}(T_+ + T_-) f$$

These operators are closely related to the Hilbert transform, whose isometric properties were studied by Poincaré. The following result is from [3].

$$TT = \frac{1}{4}I, TT_+ = \frac{1}{2}T_+, TT_- = -\frac{1}{2}T_-, T_+ = T + \frac{1}{2}I, T_- = T - \frac{1}{2}I,$$

where I is the identity operator $If = f$. The reduction to a Riemann-Hilbert boundary value problem can now be formulated as follows. Let

$$\Psi_+(k) = R(k)\Psi_-(k) + G(k), \quad (4)$$

$$\lim_{\text{Re}(k) \rightarrow \infty} \Psi_+(k) = 0 \text{ as } \text{Im}(k) \geq 0, \lim_{\text{Re}(k) \rightarrow -\infty} \Psi_-(k) = 0 \text{ as } \text{Im}(k) \leq 0 \quad (5)$$

$$\Gamma_+(k) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\ln(R(t))dt}{t - k - i0}, \Gamma_-(k) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\ln(R(t))dt}{t - k + i0}$$

$$X_+(k) = e^{\Gamma_+(k)}, X_-(k) = e^{\Gamma_-(k)}, R(k) = X_-(k)/X_+(k),$$

Then

$$\Psi_+(k) = \frac{X_+(k)}{2\pi i} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{G(t)}{X_-(t)} \frac{dt}{t-k-i0}, \quad \Psi_-(k) = \frac{X_-(k)}{2\pi i} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{G(t)}{X_-(t)} \frac{dt}{t-k+i0} \quad (6)$$

Proof. Hilbert's formula and Lemma 2 gives the solution to the Riemann-Hilbert boundary value problem (4),(5) $\square$

Applying Lemma to Riemans ζ function we get Let

$\dots s_{-n}, s_{-n} \dots s_{-n+1} \dots s_{-1}, s_1, s_2 \dots s_n \dots$ is zeros ζ function

$$Im(s) = const$$

$$Im(s_i) < Im(s) < Im(s_{i+1})$$

$$P(s) = \sum_{j \geq 1} \frac{1}{p_j^s}, \quad Re(s) > 1 + \delta, \delta > 0,$$

$$P(s) = \ln(\zeta(s) - Q(s) \quad Re(s) > 1/2 + \delta,$$

$$Q(s) = \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} P(ns)/n, \quad Re(s) > 1/2 + \delta,$$

$$\psi_+(k) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_0^1 \frac{(\ln(\zeta(s))) e^{i2kRe(s)} \theta(1/2 - \delta - Re(s)) dRe(s)}{k + i\alpha}$$

$$\psi_-(k) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_0^1 \ln(\zeta(s^*) - Q(s^*)) e^{-i2kRe(s)} \theta(Re(s) - 1/2 - \delta) dRe(s)$$

$$\tilde{\Phi}(k) = \int_0^1 \frac{s}{2} \ln(\pi) - \ln(\Gamma(s/2)) - \frac{1-s}{2} \ln(\pi) + \ln(\Gamma(1-s)/2) + Q(1-s) e^{i2kRe(s)} \theta(1/2 - \delta - Re(s)) dRe(s)$$

$$\tilde{F}(k) = \frac{\tilde{\Phi}(k)}{k + i\alpha}$$

$$G(k) = \psi_-(k) + F(k)$$

Then

$$\sup_{s, Im s_n < Im s < Im s_{n+1}} |\ln(|\zeta(s)|) \theta(Re(s) - 1/2 - \delta)| < \frac{5CC_{Im(s)}}{\delta} \quad (7)$$

Proof. Taking the logarithm from (3) and then multiplying it by $e^{i2kRe(s)}$, and after integrating by $\{Re(s), Re(s) - 1/2 > \delta\}$ we get

$$\psi_+ = \frac{e^{i2k}}{k + i\alpha} \psi_- + \tilde{F}(k) = \left(\frac{e^{i2k}}{k + i\alpha} - 1 \right) \psi_- + \psi_- + \tilde{F}(k) = R(k) \psi_- + G(k)$$

By Lemma 3 we get

$$\psi_+(k) = \frac{X_+(k)}{2\pi i} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{G(t)}{X_-(t)} \frac{dt}{t-k-i0} = X_+(k) T_+ \frac{G}{X_-} \quad (8)$$

$$\psi_-(k) = \frac{X_-(k)}{2\pi i} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{G(t)}{X_-(t)} \frac{dt}{t-k+i0} = X_-(k) T_- \frac{G}{X_-} \quad (9)$$

$$\psi_+(k) = X_+(k)T_+ \frac{G}{X_-} \quad (10)$$

$$\psi_-(k) = X_-(k)T_- \frac{G}{X_-} \quad (11)$$

(10,11) $\Rightarrow$

$$\frac{\psi_+}{X_+} - \frac{\psi_-}{X_-} = T_+ \frac{G}{X_-} - T_- \frac{G}{X_-} \Rightarrow$$

$$\frac{\psi_+}{X_+} - \frac{\psi_-}{X_-} = \frac{G}{X_-} = \frac{\psi_-}{X_-} + \frac{\tilde{F}}{X_-}$$

$$2 \frac{\psi_-}{X_-} = \frac{\psi_+}{X_+} - \frac{\tilde{F}}{X_-}$$

$$\left| \frac{\psi_-}{X_-} \right|_{k=\pi n} < \left| \frac{\tilde{F}}{X_-} \right|_{k=\pi n} + \left| \frac{\int_0^1 (\ln(\zeta(s))) e^{i2kRe(s)} \theta(1/2 - \delta - Re(s)) ds}{k - i\alpha} \right|_{k=\pi n}$$

$$\phi_- = \int_0^1 (\ln(\zeta(s))) e^{i2kRe(s)} \theta(1/2 - \delta - Re(s)) ds|_{k=\pi n}$$

$$\left| \frac{\psi_-}{X_-} \right|_{k=\pi n} < \left| \frac{\tilde{F}}{X_-} \right|_{k=\pi n} + \left| \frac{\phi_-}{k - i\alpha} \right|_{k=\pi n}$$

Lemma (2,3) $\Rightarrow$

$$X_+(k) = 1 + O(1/k), \quad X_-(k) = 1 + O(1/k),$$

Theorem of Baclund $\Rightarrow |\phi_-| \in L_2$

$$|\psi_-|_{k=\pi n} < |\tilde{F}|_{k=\pi n} + \frac{|\phi_-|}{k}|_{k=\pi n}$$

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} |\psi_-|_{k=\pi n} < \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} |\tilde{F}|_{k=\pi n} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{|\phi_-|}{k}|_{k=\pi n}$$

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} |\psi_-|_{k=\pi n} < \frac{C}{\delta} + \sqrt{\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} |\phi_-|^2|_{k=\pi n} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k^2}|_{k=\pi n}}$$

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} |\psi_-|_{k=\pi n} < \frac{C}{\delta} + \sqrt{C_{Im(s)} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k^2}|_{k=\pi n}} < \frac{3CC_{Im(s)}}{\delta}$$

Behaviour of the argument of the Riemann zeta function on the critical line by [6] $\Rightarrow$

$$|\ln|\zeta(s^*) - Q(s^*)|\theta(Re(s) - 1/2 - \delta)| < \frac{3CC_{Im(s)}}{\delta} + |Q(s)| < \frac{4CC_{Im(s)}}{\delta}$$

$$\Rightarrow \sup_s |\ln|\zeta(s^*)|\theta(Re(s) - 1/2 - \delta)| < \frac{5CC_{Im(s)}}{\delta}$$

□

Analog of Theorem Davenport-Heilbronn

Let

$$H(s)$$

is entire function

$$U(s) = H(s(1-s))$$

then

$$\zeta(s)U(s)$$

is solution Riemann's functional equation.

Proof. $\square$

$$\ln H(t) \Big|_{t=1-s} = \ln(H(1-s)s)$$

$$\ln(\zeta(s)H(s)) = \ln(\zeta(s)) + \ln H(s) = \ln(\zeta(s)) + \ln H(1-s)$$

Riemann conjecture is true

Proof. By Theorem Landau [5]

$$P(s) = \ln(\zeta(s) - Q(s)), \quad \text{Re}(s) > 1/2 + \delta,$$

let

$$\ln \mu(s) = v(s) + Q(s)$$

and $\mu(s)$ another solution (3) and $\mu(s)$ analitical in $(s_i < \text{Im}(s) < s_{i+1})$

$$v(s) \Big|_{\text{Re}(s) > 1, s_i < \text{Im}(s) < s_{i+1}} = (\ln(\zeta(s)) - Q(s)) \Big|_{\text{Re}(s) > 1, s_i < \text{Im}(s) < s_{i+1}}$$

then

$$v(s) \Big|_{\text{Re}(s) > 1/2, s_i < \text{Im}(s) < s_{i+1}} = (\ln(\zeta(s)) - Q(s)) \Big|_{\text{Re}(s) > 1/2, s_i < \text{Im}(s) < s_{i+1}} = P(s)$$

from last statement and the estimate Theorem (1-2) and its symmetry between ψ_+ and ψ_- relative to the critical line leads to the fact that there can be zero zeta-functions only on the critical line that completes the proof.

$\square$

The results of this paper, together with the results of Voronin's theorem [7] on the universality of the Riemann zeta function, lead to the following applications

4. Applications

- Information compression and information transfer,
- Seismic exploration ,
- Optimal control of oil and gas production ,
- Optimal control of oil and gas transfer,
- Control of heat and mass transfer in thermonuclear processes,
- Digitalization of technological processes,
- Earthquake predictions,
- Stock market forecast,
- Stock market forecast,
- Generations of quantum computers and quantum computing
- Seismic exploration
- Tomography
- Early diagnosis of diseases

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